

MAHMUD ZAMAKHSHARI'S LEGACY IN THE RECOGNITION OF SCIENTISTS

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Abstract. *The article presents the opinions and research works of several world scientists about the famous Eastern encyclopedic thinker Mahmud Zamakhshari, as well as the number of works of the scholar cited in various research works, their unanimous number, and brief descriptions.*

Keywords: *Mahmud Zamakhshari, Qur'anic Exegesis, Arabic language, literature, divan, geography.*

In the 10th-12th centuries, science was highly developed in Central Asia, especially the state of Khorezm, and many scientists emerged. During this period, a number of great scientists worked in the country, including Qasim al-Khwarizmi, Abu Is'haq al-Mu'izzi, Mutahhir ibn Safid an-Nuzkasi, Yakut Suhayli, Beruni, Hassan an-Naysaburi, Mahmud az-Zamakhshari, Abu Yaqub as-Sakkaki, Mutarizi, Ali ibn Muhammad al-Imrani, and Hassan al-Khwarizmi. Among them, Mahmud Zamakhshari was an encyclopedic scholar who wrote his rare works on several areas of science.

The scholar's full name is Abu-l-Qasim Mahmud ibn Umar ibn Muhammad, and in some sources it is Ahmad. According to Ubaydulla Uvatov, he wrote about himself in a letter:

"I am Mahmud ibn Umar ibn Muhammad ibn Ahmad al-Khwarizmi, then az-Zamakhshari. I belong to a village (Zamakhshar) in Khorezm. Zamakhshar is my birthplace."

Mahmud Zamakhshari was born on Wednesday, March 19, 1075 AD, on the twenty-seventh day of Rajab, 467 AH, in Zamakhshar, one of the largest villages in Khorezm.

Mahmud Zamakhshari's father, although not very wealthy, was a literate, very pious, and religious man of his time. He spent most of his time reciting the Quran and praying. He also served as an imam in a mosque in Zamakhshari. He was a good-natured, sweet-spoken, and very kind person. With this quality, he gained great respect and admiration among the people. His mother was also considered a pious, religious, and kind-hearted woman.

Mahmud Zamakhshari received his initial education in his homeland from his father. Then he continued his education in a madrasa. Here he fully and thoroughly mastered various fields of science, especially the Arabic language and literature, the complex of religious sciences, and the art of calligraphy, which was valued in his time. Later, in order to further improve his knowledge, he went to Bukhara, which was the center of science in his time. Here he studied with outstanding professors and returned to his homeland. During his blessed life, the scholar traveled to several cities – Merv, Nishapur, Isfahan, Damascus, Baghdad, Hejaz and Mecca, and wrote many rare works.

The first information about the life and work of Mahmud Zamakhshari is given in the work “Nasabnama” by the famous scientist Abu Sa’d Abdulkarim ibn Muhammad ibn Mansur At-Tamimi as-Sam’ani. According to the source, the scholar “was said to be a famous Arabic linguist and writer. He went to Iraq in search of knowledge. He lived in Mecca for several years near the Kaaba. He listened to hadith from famous professors. He wrote works on tafsir, hadith, nahw and other fields. He also has poetry collections.” After the scientist, there are valuable information in a number of sources, including Ibn Khallikan’s “Wafyotu-l-a’yan wa anbo’ abno’i-z-zamon”, Ibn al-Anbari’s “Nuzhatu-l-alibba fi tabaqati-l-udabo”, Yaqut al-Hamawi’s “Mu’jamu-l-buldan”, al-Yafi’i’s “Mir’out-l-jinan”, Ibn al-Jawzi’s “Al-Muntazam”, Jalaluddin as-Suyuti’s “Bughyotu-l-ruwat”, Ibn al-Qifti’s “Inbahu-r-ruwat”, and Haji Khalifa’s “Kashfu-z-zunun”.

There are also many confessions about the scholar’s scientific activities and qualities. Among them, the famous Egyptian Historian ibn Taghribardi expressed the following opinion: “The sheikh was a great scholar, the only one of his time, the leader and imam of his century.” Arab scientists said: “The Arabs could not conquer Transoxiana with weapons, but the scholar from Khorezm conquered the entire Arab world with his staff.” The famous Iraqi historian Ibn Khallikan has the following information: “Zamakhshari is a great imam in tafsir, hadith, nahw, dictionary and ilmu-l-bayan. Without any exaggeration, he was the only one of his time in these sciences, the author of many wonderful works”

World orientalist have shown great interest in the scholar’s heritage and have conducted many of their own studies. Among them are Brockelman, Besing, Gibb, Goldsier, Neldeke, Wright, I. Y. Krachkovsky, V. M. Belkin, V. V. Bartold, A. K. Borovkov, A. Krimsky, B. Boqir, F. Qabova, L. E. Leopold, A. Noy and O. Capezio. From our country, Y. Islamov, A. Rustamov, U. Uvatov, Sh. Madayev, Z. Islamov, O. Qoriyev, A. Kayumov, N. Sulaymanova, D. Khudzhanova and L. Turayev have conducted extensive research on the scholar’s scientific heritage. Several studies have been compiled on the scholar’s life and scientific legacy, including “Ad-Dirasat annahwiya wa-l-lughawiyya ind-az-Zamakhshari” (“The Grammatical and Lexical Teachings of Az-Zamakhshari”) by the scientist of the Baghdad University, Fazil Salih as-Samari, “Az-Zamakhshari Lughawiy” (“The Lexicographer Az-Zamakhshari”) by Murtaza Ayatilla al-Shirazi, and “Al-Adab ul-Arabiy fi iqlim Khwarazm” (“Arabic Literature in the Land of Khorezm”) by the Palestinian scholar Hind Hussein Taha.

We know that Mahmud Zamakhshari was productive in several areas of science. We witness that the number of his works is cited differently in several sources. For example, the German orientalist Karl Brockelmann’s book “Geschichte der arabischen litteratur” in German, published in 1898, mentions 21 works of the scholar in the 1st edition, and 25 in the 2nd edition. According to another his work “History of Arab Literature” in Arabic, published in Egypt, mentions 31 works of the scholar. The two-volume work “Kashu-z-zunun” by Arab Researcher Haji Khalifa listed 29 works of the scholar. The Iraqi historian Ibn Khallikan’s “Wafyotu-l-a’yan wa anbo’ abnou’i-z-zaman” lists the names of 30 of his works. Alibek Rustamov’s “Mahmud Zamakhshari” provides information about 38 of the scholar’s works in total. Ahmad Muhammad al-Khufi’s “Az-Zamakhshari”, published in Cairo, mentions the existence of 48 of his works. In Yakut al-Hamawi’s “Mu’jamu-l-buldon” this figure was 50. According to Ubaydulla Uvatov’s “Nozik iboralar”, the scholar’s works are more than 50. We can also see that this number is recorded in the National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan. The Encyclopedia of Islam provides information about 54 works of the scholar. According to the source, Muhammad Basil Uyun as-Sud lists 65 works of Mahmud Zamakhshari in his research and provides detailed information

about some of them. According to the “Assalom” newspaper of the Dagestan Muslim Administration, it is said that about 20 works of the scholar exist, and only the names of about 50 works are known. Nigora Sulaymanova’s research indicates that the number of works compiled by Mahmud Zamakhshari is about 70, and, ultimately, the view is put forward that the total number of the scholar’s works may be even greater. One of the recent studies, Laziz Turayev’s dissertation, acknowledges that their number is more than 80. The names of the scholar’s works known to us and brief information about them are given in the table below.

№	Title of scholar’s works	Brief description
1	“A’jabu-l-a’jab fi sharhi lamiyati-l-‘arab”	Wonder of wonders thoughts in the commentary of “Lamiyati-l-‘arab”
2	“Ad-Duru-d-dairu-l-muntahab min kinayat wa isti’arat wa tashbihat”	“Selected gems from Arabic irony, metaphor and simile”. In some sources it is also cited as “Ad-Dur ad-dair al-muntahab fi kitabat wa isti’arat wa tashbihat il-arab” (“Selected gems from Arabic literature, metaphor and simile”).
3	“Al-‘Unmuzaj fi-n-nahw”	“A model in the science of nahw”. A summary of “Al-Mufassal”.
4	“Al-Amaliy fi-n-nahwi”	“Orthography in Grammatical Rules”
5	“Al-asmo fi-l-lughat”	“Names in Language”
6	“Alfaiq fi gharibi-l-hadith”	“Comments on some places in the dictionary of “Gharibi-l-hadith” ”
7	«Al-Kashf fi-l-qirat»	“Discovery in Recitation”
8	“Al-Kashshof ’an haqqaiqi ghawomizu-t-tanzil va ’uyuni-l-aqawil fi wujuhi-t-ta’wil”	“Opening the Eyes of Narrations by Interpreting the Hidden Truths in the Quran”
9	“Al-mas’ala fi kalimati-sh-shahoda”	“Question about the Word of Testimony” or “Issue about the Word of Testimony”
10	“Al-Mawridu-r-raiq fi-l-mavoiz wal-hikayat”	“Original sources in sermons and stories”
11	“Al-Minhaj fi usuli-d-din”	“The path to the foundations of religion”
12	“Al-Mufassal fi ilmi-l-arabiyya”	“A detailed book on the Arabic language”
13	“Al-Mufassal fi san’ati-l-i’rab”	“A detailed book on the art of inflection”
14	“Al-Mufrad wa-l-muallaf fi-n-nahwi”	“Singularity and Plurality in Grammar”. In another source it is cited as “Al-Mufrad wa-l-mu’laf fi-n-nahw” (“Singularity and Plurality in Grammar”)
15	“Al-Muftad wa-l makbakab fi-l-arabiya”	“Singularity and Plurality in Arabic”
16	“Al-Muhazarat wa-l-muhavarat”	“Lectures and Conversations”
17	“Al-Muhajat bi-l-masayl an-nahwiya ab al-ahajiy an-nahwiya”	“Riddles on Grammar Issues”. The name of the work is also cited in the sources as “Al-Muhajat fil-ahajiy wal alg‘az”; “Muhajatu annahwiya”

		(“Grammar Issues”) and “Alghazun wa masoilu nahwiya” (“Vocabularies and Grammar Issues”)
18	“Al-Muhajat wa mutammim mahommi arbabi-l-muhajat”	
19	“Al-Mu’jamu-l-arabiyu-l-farsiy”	“Arabic-Persian Dictionary” or “Arabic-Persian Dictionary”
20	“Al-Mustaqsa fi-l-amsolu-l-arab”	“On the in-depth study of Arabic proverbs and sayings”. Also cited in sources as “Al-Mustaqsa fi-l-amsol” (“On the in-depth study of proverbs”)
21	“Al-Qasidatu-l-ba’uziya”	“Ode about the Mosquito”. The name of the work is also cited in sources as “Al-Qasidatu-l-ba’uziya wa ukhro fi masoili-l-Gha’azzoliy” (“Ode on the “Ba’uziya” in Gha'azzoliy issues and others”)
22	“Al-Qistasu-l-mustaqim fi ilmi-l-arud”	“The True Criteria of the Science of Prosody”. We have also learned in the sources that the title of the work is given as “Al-Qistas fi ilmi-l-arud” (“The Criteria of the Science of Prosody”)
23	“Ar-Raiz fi-ilmi-l-faroiz”	“Exercise on the science of inheritance law”
24	“Asosu-l-baloghah”	“Fundamentals of eloquence”
25	“Atwaqu-dhahab fi-l-mavo’iz va-l-khutab”	“Golden ornaments of sermons and advice”. In short, “Atwaqu-dhahab” (“Golden ornaments”)
26	“Divan-sh-shi’r”	“Poetic Diwan”
27	“Divan-z-Zamakhshari”	“Zamakhshari’s Diwan”
28	“Divan-r-rasail”	“Diwan about messages”
29	“Diwan-t-tamsiyi”	“Diwan about assimilation”. The sources also cite the title of the work as “Divan-t-tamoyil”
30	“Faiq al-lughat”	
31	“Ilmu-l-tassvvuf”	“Knowledge of Sufism”
32	“Jawahiru-l-lughat”	“Jewels of the language”
33	“Kitab al-jibal wa-l-amkina wa-l-miyah”	“Book about mountains, places and waters”. Also cited in the sources as “Al-Amkina wa-l-jibal wa-l-miyah” (“Places, mountains and waters”)
34	“Kitabu khasaisu-l-ashara al-kirami-l-barara”	“Book about the characteristics of ten generous people” or “Book about the characteristics of ten generous, virtuous people”
35	“Maqamat”	“Status”. Also cited in the sources as “Maqamatu-z-Zamakhshari” (“Status of Az-Zamakhshari”)
36	“Marsiya fi shaykhihi Abu Muzir fi-l-maznun li-l-ghuzo”	
37	“Muqaddimatu-l-adab”	“Introduction to the science of literary studies”. In some sources it is also cited as “Muqaddimatu-l-adab fi-l-lughat” (“Introduction to literary studies in language”)
38	“An-Nasaihu-s-sighar wal-l-bavolighul-kibor”	“The devotion of the little ones and the maturity of the great ones”. In some sources the title of the work is divided into two and is also cited as

		“Nasaih ul-kibar” (“Advice to the great ones”) and “Nasaih us-sighar” (“Advice to the little ones”)
39	“Nawabihu-l-kalim”	“Wise words” or “Delicate expressions”
40	“Nukat ul-arab fi gharibi-l-irab”	“The elegance of the Arabs in the wonderful expression of the Quran”
41	“Nuzhat ul-mustanis”	“The pleasure of companions” or “The comfort of friends”
42	“Qasida fi suoli-l-Ghazali an julusillah ala-l-arsh va qusuri-l-ma’rifa”	“An ode dedicated to Ghazali’s question about “The place of Allah on the Throne and the imperfection of knowledge in man”
43	“Qasoid ukhro”	“Other odes”
44	“Rhythm”	A book written about Arabic nahw (syntax) and taught as a textbook in madrasas. Jami’s work “Sharhi mullah” is dedicated to this “Rhythm”
45	“Rabi’ al-abrar wa nusuh ul-akhbar”	“Spring of the Good and the Commentary on the Chronicles”. In some sources it is also cited as “Rabi’ al-abrar wa nusuh ul-akhbar”. According to recent research, it is suggested that the title of the work should be more correctly called “Rabi’ al-abrar wa nusuh al-akhbar fi al-muhozarat” (“Spring of the Good and the Commentary on the Science of Lectures”)
46	“Risala fi hikmat ush-shahoda wa ukhra fi nass ul-asharo”	“Treatise on the wisdom of the testimony and a document about ten other people”
47	“Risala fi ma jaro min-l-muhawarat”	“Treatise on the conclusions of conversation”
48	“Risala fi-l-majaz wa-l-isti’ara”	“Treatise on metaphor and isti’ara”
49	“Risalatul-tasarrufat”	“Treatise on manners”
50	“Ru’usu-l-masa’il fi-l-fiqh”	“The beginning of the issues of fiqh”
51	“Samiymu-l-arabiya”	“The basis of the Arabic language” or “The essence of the Arabic language”
52	“Sharhu abyati kitab Sibawayh”	“Commentary on the couplets of the book of Sibawayh”
53	“Sharhu-l-fasih”	“Perfect commentary”
54	“Sharhu-l-maqamat”	Commentary on the “Maqamat”
55	“Sharhu-l-Mufassal”	“Commentary on the Mufassal”. In another source it is also cited as “Sharhu ba’zi mushkilati-l-Mufassal” (“Commentary on some of the unclear problems of the “Mufassal” ”)
56	“Ta’limu-l-mubtadiy wa irshadu-l-muqtadiy”	“Teaching the beginning and showing the way to the follower”
The following works are cited in A. Rustamov’s research as sources which titles are known but have not yet been found:		
57	“Divanu xutab”	

58	“Divanu-t-tamsil”
59	“Mu’jamu-l-hudud”
60	“Muxtasaru-l-muvofiqa bayna ahli-l-bayt va-s-sahoba”
61	“Risolat-l-asror”
62	“Risolatu-l-mas’ama”
63	“Risolatu-n-nosiha”
64	“Savoirul-l-amsol”
65	“Shaqoiqu-n-nu’mon fi haqoiqi-n-nu’mon”
66	“Shofiyu-l-’ay”
67	“Tasliyatu-z-zarir”
68	“Zolatu-n-noshid va-r-roiz fi ’ilmi-l-faroiz”

In conclusion, according to U. Uvatov, Mahmud Zamakhshari’s deep knowledge, genius, and immortal works in various fields of science brought him great fame throughout the Muslim East during his lifetime. The scholar was called with deep respect and affection by such honorable names as “Ustodu-l-arab va-l-ajam” (“Teacher of Arabs and non-Arabs”), “Fakhru Khwarezm” (“Pride of Khorezm”). He was always one of the leaders in the circle of famous scientists, poets, and writers, and his opinion was taken into account in heated scientific debates and discussions. We learned this from the recognition of many world scientists in their memoirs and genealogies.

We have witnessed the fact that the number of works of the scholar is cited differently in several sources. Based on recent research, more than eighty works by Mahmud Zamakhshari are considered to exist.

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